

THE PROBLEM OF EXISTENTIALISM IN JAPANESE PHILOSOPHY

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Abstract: The modern world is a complex system of contradictory paradigms and mentalities. Understanding their mutual assimilation and historical confrontations is essential in creating a unified picture of the world. Japanese culture and philosophy contain the foundations on which the paradigm pole is built, which is different from Western European consciousness. But even in the Eastern worldview, Japan occupies a special position. All this gave rise to a different, sometimes paradoxical, but logical mentality. The special philosophical heritage of the history of Japan allows us to speak of a separate, independent style of Eastern philosophizing.

Key words: existentialism, Buddhism, philosophy of Nishida Kitaro.

Philosophy of Japan in the 20th century. thanks to the Meiji restoration, which took place in 1868, she managed to move away from the religious and mythological worldview and, actively perceiving the philosophical concepts of the West, managed to create her own, original philosophical trends and theories. The philosophical concept of "existence" (existencia) gained popularity in European philosophy at the end of the 19th century. In Japan, philosophical thinking, or simply existentialism, had its development in the writings of various philosophers. The emergence of existential philosophy in Europe indicates that the old form of philosophy, which aimed to explore the very root and essence of the world, no longer provided the answers needed by modern man. And what existential philosophy is concerned with is nothing but human existence and reality. When European philosophy freed itself from the shackles imposed on man by the philosophy of reason and positivism, it found free will as its last resort. By comparison, philosophers in Japan and Taiwan have done the same. It was by means of which they presented, interpreted and internalized existential thinking that they applied philosophy to their own existence. Taking as a starting point the spread of existentialism in modern Japan, this article traces and describes the introduction and interpretation of Tanabe Hajime (1885-1962) as European existential thinking, due to the association with the religious understanding of existence. Based on its research, this article hopes to offer some reflection on the development and significance of existentialism in East

Asia. Under the influence of the established mode of production, not only economic, but also traditional social ties were destroyed, which led to changes in the Japanese spiritual sphere. These changes were also influenced by the assimilation of the values of Western civilization, and the foreign spiritual culture was perceived by the Japanese at first as a kind of monolith, a single whole. A landmark figure for Japanese philosophy at the beginning of the century was Nishida Kitaro, the leader of the Kyoto school, who created his own original theory on the basis of Western philosophy of existentialism. Most of the participants in this trend were followers and commentators of Nishida's theories. In addition to them, it included almost all the leading thinkers of their time. The Kyoto school was a powerful idealist movement, which not only created its own theories on the basis of existentialism, but was also of decisive importance for the development of Japanese philosophy as a whole.

The name comes from the Late Latin word *existentia*, which literally means "existence". Existentialism is often referred to as the "philosophy of existence". The central concept in philosophy is existence (that is, human existence), the main modes (manifestations) of human existence are care, determination, conscience, fear. It is also worth noting that a person "sees through existence as the root of his being in borderline situations"[2] (in struggle, suffering, death). Studying oneself as an existence, a person acquires freedom, which "is the choice of oneself, one's essence, which imposes responsibility on him for everything that happens in the world"[3].

The main problem of existentialism is the problem of a spiritual crisis, where a person finds himself due to certain life circumstances, and the choice that he ultimately makes in order to get out of this crisis. The signs of the crisis, scientists include fear, "existential anxiety", nausea, boredom.

Throughout the history of the country, an important, and often dominant place in the public consciousness belonged to religious and ethical teachings, and especially Buddhism. In Japan, two tendencies of Buddhist thought became widespread, indicating two possibilities for self-disclosure of the essence of man. The first assumed self-disclosure through the involvement of the individual in social life and the subordination of all of his interests to society. The second, on the contrary, called for flight from social ties as untrue, and cultivated the ideal of seclusion. The penetration of Confucianism into Japan dates back to the 4th century BC. Neighboring with Buddhism and gradually gaining strength during the 12th-16th centuries, Confucianism by the 17th century. took the place of the dominant ideology there. The Buddhist-Confucian tradition continued to

dominate the spiritual life of society until the second half of the 19th century. In other words, Shinto determined the religious and mythological form of the traditional spiritual culture of the Japanese people. However, this culture cannot be understood without considering the influence of Buddhism on it. The assertion of the Buddhist teaching, which came from India through China into the spiritual life of Japanese society, took place approximately in the 7th century. Since then, this doctrine, either rising to the rank of an official religion (VIII-XIV centuries), or being persecuted (XVI century), acquiring various shades in accordance with specific socio-political conditions, eventually firmly rooted in the national consciousness of the Japanese.

In Japan, two tendencies of Buddhist thought became widespread, pointing out two ways to save the essence of man. The first assumed personal self-realization through the involvement of the individual in social life and the subordination of all his interests to the interests of society. The second, on the contrary, called for an escape from social ties as untrue and cult. In Japan, existentialism began to assert its position in the 30s and 40s of the XX century. and became especially popular in the post-war period. The emergence and spread of existentialism here was due, in our opinion, to two reasons. Firstly, there was a certain similarity between existentialist and Buddhist worldviews traditional for Japanese culture. The same closeness, thanks to which the phenomenon of "perception through recognition" already described above became possible. In particular, Heidegger's creative method is very consonant with the Japanese thought tradition, since "it consists in understanding the explicit through the implicit, what is said through what cannot be said, to understand the word through silence, the existent through the non-existent, being is through nothing." [3] "Nothing," writes Heidegger, "is that very being, to the truth of which a person is entrusted when he has overcome the subject in himself and when, therefore, he no longer represents the existent as an object ... The hidden essence of being, ordered impregnability, is most directly exposed as in general non-existent, like nothing." [4] The proximity of these provisions to the ideas of Buddhist ontology is obvious. promoted the ideal of hermitage.

Nishido has always been interested in contradictions in European thought. The philosopher is trying to understand the reasons for these contradictions, putting forward the thesis that the center of European thought has always been "being", conceived as a "process", which also echoes Martin Heidegger's thought about the positive direction of new European thought that gave birth to science. Being, understood as a process, does not allow the freedom of the "individual", since it

presupposes a universal causal connection. The philosophical thought of Nishido Kitaro is so universal and amazing, as it gives us not just existentialism, but a synthesis of existentialism and Buddhist philosophy. In particular, Nishido's idea of being as a process that does not allow the freedom of the "individual" undoubtedly resembles the Buddhist concept of the universal interconnectedness and interdependence of existence. Nishido Kitaro believes that if these conditions are taken as initial, then the explanation of the nature of the "individual", including personal freedom in society, it will become impossible.[5] In an effort to thematize and justify freedom, Nishido argues that universally - the general must be such that it "exists" defining its general character.

"individual" and their connection with each other, and at the same time "do not exist as a certain something that determines the "individual" and destroys their independence. Such a universal general, having the characteristic of "absolute non-being", which ensures in its infinity the independence and freedom of the "individual", and by its general character - their connection. In terms of content, it is revealed by the Japanese philosopher as a specific general, determined by itself. It is self-determination of consciousness, subject, spirit and, thus, self-knowledge. Self-knowledge is considered by the philosopher as "intuition", as the contemplation of oneself in oneself Nishido Kitaro asserts and emphasizes that "absolute being" has a non-substantial nature. To prove and visualize his thought, the Japanese philosopher, describing self-consciousness, uses such expressions of Buddhist thought as "contemplation without a contemplator" and definition without a determiner. In European existential philosophy, it is customary to single out the cognizing subject.

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